

Education Quarterly Reviews

Denizci, C. (2022). Multimodal Differentiation for Allophone Pupils in First Language French Classroom. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.5 Special Issue 2: Current Education Research in Turkey, 417-428.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.04.633

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Multimodal Differentiation for Allophone Pupils in First Language French Classroom

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Abstract

Language classroom interactions can be characterized as multimodal, since teachers may resort to a variety of resources provided by their body or by their immediate space in order to convey meaning, manage activities and assess pupils' performances. Furthermore, teachers' multimodal practices constitute an essential component for the differentiating process aiming to resolve especially linguistic problems some pupils may face. In this perspective, this study examines the implementation of multimodal differentiation by the same teacher in the case of allophone pupils following first language French courses alongside with native pupils of 3rd grade within the context of inclusion classroom in a middle school in France. More specifically, it was aimed to analyze a teacher's adaptation of kinesic and proxemic behaviors within the differentiation process, such as the use of hand gestures, gaze and facial expressions as bodily resources but also the control of interpersonal distance with respect to allophone pupils. For this purpose, a micro-ethnographic research strategy was applied, and data was collected through video-recorded sessions of the teacher in inclusion classroom. Our qualitative analysis of the data revealed a differentiated use of prosodic, kinesic and proxemic elements by the teacher, such as the reduction of speech rate, the accentuation of words, the production of deictic and iconic hand gestures as well as facial expressions, the orientation of gaze, the forward leaning posture, the isolated seating arrangement, and the reduction of interpersonal distance. All these elements either follow or overlap each other, especially within the framework of teacher instructions during classroom activities.

Keywords: Multimodality, Differentiation, Teaching of French, Allophone Pupils, Gesture, Proxemics

1. Introduction

1.1 Problematic of the Study

This study deals with the multimodal treatment of linguistic gaps occurring in the case of allophone pupils within the pedagogical differentiation put forward by the same teacher. In order to delve into this problematic, the data based on the natural video-recorded courses of the same teacher was collected in a middle school in France (i.e. a category of school also called "college", which provides the first cycle of the secondary education in the country), where allophone pupils (i.e. migrant teenagers who had newly arrived in France and whose mother tongues were not French) were following first language French (FLF) courses within the inclusion classroom alongside with native French pupils of 3rd grade.

The importance of the topic in question emerges from our informal observation about a similar linguistic proficiency gap encountered with pupils learning French as a foreign language (FFL) in Turkey. For the purpose of remedying the linguistic ability differences showing up among FFL pupils in Turkey, teacher practices and/or actions involving multimodal differentiation (i.e. the adaptation of teacher actions such as hand gestures, facial expressions, gaze, posture, use of personal distance, etc. in favor of allophone pupils) are brought into consideration in this paper.

When taking into account the role of kinesics (use of body language co-occurring with speech) and/or proxemics (use of space and interpersonal distance) in FFL/FLF teaching (also in Second Language French settings), there are few experimental and empirical studies handling the issue of multimodal teacher practices about how language teachers adapt their body movements and/or distancing to enhance the transmission of meaning to non-native speakers (Tellier, 2016; Azaoui, 2017a, 2017b, 2019a; Walper, 2019; Stam & Tellier, 2021; Castany-Owhadi & Azaoui, 2022 among others). As far as the multimodality in differentiated teacher practices is concerned, Benzakki and Mendonça Dias (2022) mention for instance the use of kinesics as a pedagogical aid among language teachers communicating with allophone pupils in France, Luxembourg and Quebec; however, the authors deriving their data from a survey do not give details about the way teachers make use of kinesics. In another study establishing links between multimodality and differentiation, Azaoui and Denizci (2022) empirically observe in a French middle school a teacher communicating with allophone students during inclusion courses (FLF setting) as well as those confined solely to the same allophone students (FSL setting); the authors highlight the teacher's abundant and conscious resort to multimodal differentiation.

The objective of the present study consists in analyzing the multimodal differentiation for allophone students in FLF context and drawing from there pedagogical implications for the teaching of French as a foreign language in Turkey. We contend that the FLF classroom with allophones lays a suitable ground for studying multimodal differentiation. In this perspective, our research question is as follows: How a language teacher adapts her/his kinesic and proxemic behaviors (also the prosodic ones when relevant) in order to overcome linguistic problems occurring among allophone pupils? To find answers to this question, an 80-minute video-recorded data obtained from a teacher providing FLF courses to both native and allophone pupils attending an inclusion classroom within a middle school in France (therefore, in a natural instructional setting) was analyzed as a case study.

1.2 Relevance of the Study

As previously mentioned in the subsection 1.1, the relevance of the present study arises from its possible implications to draw for FFL settings in Turkey. More specifically, as there are linguistic level discrepancies in most cases between pupils of the same classroom, foreign language teachers should endeavor to make their linguistically weaker pupils attain course objectives within the group. Hence, the multimodal differentiation in teacher practices should be taken into account.

To our point of view, the present study can be described as relevant, for it intends to contribute to the understanding of multimodal differentiation in terms of language teachers' kinesic and proxemic behaviors for the FLF setting. It partly aims to draw conclusions for the FFL setting from the analysis.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

Human interactions are considered as inherently multimodal (Goffman, 1956), i.e. various kinesic (such as hand gesture primarily but also facial expression, gaze, posture, etc.) and proxemic actions (Hall, 1971) performed by a speaker co-occur with speech, cognitively relate to it, bear similar or complementary communicative functions with respect to her/his utterances, and especially give visual clues to the addressee for communicative purposes (Cosnier, 1982; Kendon, 2004; McNeill, 1992, 2005).

Similarly, this also applies to language classroom interactions which may be characterized as multimodal and multichannelled due to their socially/pedagogically organized settings (Colletta, 2000; Coquet, 2012; Tabensky, 2014). In other words, teachers (but also pupils) have recourse to a multiplicity of resources provided either by the pedagogical material (such as interactive whiteboard, video projector, chart, poster, computer, Internet,

course book or any object teachers are able to manipulate for pedagogical reasons) surrounding them or by their own body (i.e. kinesic and proxemic actions together with speech) while communicating with pupils. For this study, we are rather interested in kinesic and proxemic behaviors in conjunction with speech, thus making part of multimodality.

Moreover, teachers' verbal and non-verbal actions/practices (Cicurel, 2011) make an integral part of multimodality, so that they basically undertake three pedagogical functions: transmission of information (on morphosyntactic, semantic/lexical, phonetic levels), activity/interaction management and performance assessment/correction (Tellier, 2008).

The heterogeneity of language levels is prone to impede not only teaching practices but especially pupils' school success in general. In fact, it may lead to discouragement and even to school drop-out for pupils; therefore, pedagogical differentiation plays a crucial role in compensating for possible language level disparities among pupils; this being said, the main aim of pedagogical differentiation, inspired by the individualized educational models of 1960s in USA, consists in bringing all pupils (having different linguistic abilities and needs) to school success by accompanying each individual within the collectivity toward the same pedagogical goal (Perrenoud, 1992; Tomlinson, 2001; Tomlinson & McTighe, 2006; Jobin & Gauthier, 2008; Feyfant, 2016; Forget, 2017; David & Abry, 2018).

In the light of the above-mentioned, differentiation is defined as the implementation of a set of diverse pedagogical practices and procedures for the purpose of reaching a common goal within pupils whose linguistic levels may vary, and it comprises four essential components (Tomlinson, 1999; Tomlinson & Jarvis, 2009):

- content which refers to the conception of curriculum and, to a lesser extent, to the didactic material presented during a course to convey information (such as worksheets, course books, etc.);
- process including the planning of a course but also the verbal and non-verbal strategies utilized by the teacher in order to convey information, manage activities/interactions and assess student performances;
- production (or rather product) meaning the diverse outputs obtained from pupils (generally in the form of speaking, writing, tasks combining various linguistic skills, etc.) at the end of the differentiation process;
- and working environment regarding for example the placement of pupil desks or other pedagogical materials.

It needs to be pointed out that teachers may differentiate through one or more of these components to facilitate learning for pupils in difficulty.

1.4 Correspondence of Problematic to Research Design

The question of how a teacher adapts her/his kinesic and proxemic behaviors in a multimodal fashion when she/he interacts with pupils in linguistic difficulties stems from our problematic. To better answer the research question, the coordination of a French teacher's kinesic/proxemic practices with speech and prosody will be examined especially in terms of process as a differentiation component. More specifically, we are interested in how speech, gesture, facial expression, gaze, posture and interpersonal distance (but also prosody) are brought into play as a differentiation process by the teacher while conveying information by the intermediary of a didactic content in order to foster learning for allophone pupils facing a linguistic difficulty.

In the above-mentioned perspective, the teacher's verbal discourse was analyzed together with the corresponding non-verbal behaviors for the differentiated sequences. In brief, 80-minute video-recorded inclusion classroom (consisting of 2 sessions/courses) of the same French teacher, where allophone pupils follow FLF courses alongside with native ones, was observed from an ethnographic point of view as a case study. Yet, more details about the selected research design and the method of analysis will be given in the Method section.

2. Method

2.1 Participant

This research was supported in 2018 by the French Embassy in Turkey, which granted us a scholarship for post-doctoral studies. In the scope of the scholarship, we carried out our post-doctoral studies in the University of Montpellier during October-November 2018. For the purpose of working on multimodal differentiation, a middle school (or college) was chosen in the city of Sète, since the school was admitting allophone students within the inclusion classes (together with the native pupils of 3rd grade in the context of FLF) as well as the classes devoted only to allophones for FSL teaching. The invitation from the University of Montpellier and the consent forms signed by the video-recorded teacher and pupils were obtained.

The participant of this study consists in a French middle school teacher taking in charge simultaneously, within two instructional settings, the FLF and the FSL courses for allophone pupils. As far as the allophone pupils (around age 14-15) attending the inclusion courses are concerned, their linguistic proficiency was between A1-A2, as described in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (Council of Europe, 2020).

The selection criterion while choosing the participant was partly accessibility but primarily the participant's teaching context, i.e. she was providing French courses to both allophone and/or native pupils (respectively the Second Language French and the FLF settings). Furthermore, priority was given to the FLF classroom because we supposed that the FLF context, where allophone pupils followed courses together with native ones, was prone to multimodal differentiation more. Therefore, the participant was chosen through purposeful sampling (Merriam, 2009).

2.2 Research Design and Data Collection

On the one hand, we opted for an ethnographic research strategy (rather micro-ethnographic as our research entailed a relatively shorter period of time) to find answers to the research question, since we observed the teacher's behaviors in terms of multimodal differentiation within a group of allophone and native pupils following FLF courses in a naturalistic context; on the other hand, as we tried to effectuate an in-depth qualitative analysis of one selected teacher whose FLF classroom lent itself to a particular setting in terms of composition (i.e. allophone and native pupils) and multimodal differentiation, the present study also adheres to qualitative case study as research design (Babbie, 2010; Bryman, 2012; Paillé & Mucchielli, 2013). In consequence, the research design at issue relies on both micro-ethnography and case study.

As for the data, it was collected empirically for the same teacher through her video recordings extending to a time interval of two months; hence, an approximately 10-hour corpus was obtained, of which an 80-minute segment consisting of two FLF sessions was examined for this paper. A part of the corpus was firstly analyzed for Second Language French and FLF settings by Azaoui and Denizci (2022). In this study, it is aimed to further expand analysis by focalizing solely on the FLF setting.

2.3 Data Analysis

This study considers the notion of differentiation as multimodal. More precisely, while describing the teacher's behavioral adaptations to allophone pupils within differentiated sequences, the following parameters were taken into account: verbal discourse (its semantic content as well as its prosodic elements), hand gesture, facial expression, gaze, posture and interpersonal distance as components of multimodal differentiation process.

In this perspective, the study mainly combines discourse analysis with kinesic/proxemic analysis in the context of differentiation. Besides, the didactic content may also be differentiated, e.g. the didactic documents on which allophone pupils and native ones work may vary sometimes from one group to another. Moreover, we decided whether a sequence in the corpus was relevant or not in terms of differentiation by taking into account significant kinesic/proxemic changes observed in teaching practices in favor of the allophone pupils.

Before proceeding into the analysis of the relevant sequences of the corpus, it would be worth mentioning respectively the conventions of transcription and those concerning annotation for the teacher's utterances and kinesic/proxemic behaviors:

(a) Utterances in French are orthographically transcribed.

- (b) An utterance or a segment of utterance co-occurring with prosodic, kinesic and/or proxemic behaviors is underlined.
- (c) <Description of prosodic, kinesic and/or proxemic behaviors> is shown between arrowheads in italic letter.
- (d) An inaudible or irrelevant utterance is marked with three suspension points between square brackets [...].
- (e) (Figure number) is shown between parentheses.
- (f) *ENGLISH TRANSLATION OF AN UTTERANCE* is shown between asterisks in capital letters.
- (g) *dg* means deictic gesture.
- (h) *ig* means iconic gesture.
- (i) *fe* means facial expression.
- (j) *ga* means gaze.
- (k) *flp* means forward leaning posture.
- (l) *appr* means approach.
- (m) + represents the coordination of simultaneous or consecutive behaviors.
- (n) T means teacher.
- (o) AP means allophone pupil.

3. Results

3.1 General Observations

Our analyses of the two sessions in the FLF inclusion classroom reveal some general findings in a typical multimodally differentiated sequence:

- At linguistic level, the teacher simplifies as much as possible her sentences or prefers more simple words.
 - At prosodic level,
 - (a) she slows down her speech rate (or the flow of speech).
 - (b) she accentuates important words.
 - At proxemic level,
 - (a) the allophone pupils are seated together at the back of the classroom.
 - (b) the teacher approaches allophone pupil(s) closely.
 - At kinesic level,
 - (a) she directs her gaze to the allophone pupil(s) concerned.
 - (b) she produces a deictic hand gesture (i.e. pointing gesture performed in general by an extended forefinger with other fingers curled in the closed palm) toward a pedagogical material such as the pedagogical document, the course book, the whiteboard, etc. In some circumstances, she performs an iconic hand gesture (McNeill, 1992) or a facial expression to visually illustrate a verbal referent.
 - (c) she leans toward allophone pupil(s) (sometimes in addition to a crouch position).
- Figure 1 exemplifies below our general observation about multimodal differentiation.

Figure 1: General Characteristics of Multimodal Differentiation in Inclusion Classroom

T handles a French surrealist author named Michel Leiris' (1901-1990) book entitled "L'âge d'homme" (1939) for the purpose of working on the vocabulary linked to the expression of emotions as didactic content. She writes some keywords to the whiteboard and asks all pupils to make a summary of the author's feelings by using the written words. Before the differentiated sequence, T either remains standing in a stationary position in front of the whiteboard or sits on her desk (Figure 1a).

However, once she gives the instruction about the activity, the multimodal differentiation sequence starts. In an attempt to learn if her instruction is well understood and to clarify it if necessary, she quickly moves toward APs sitting at the back of the classroom. Hence, she brings into play a set of behaviors tied to multimodal differentiation process: First of all, she approaches APs, leans toward them and addresses them in a very low voice. That is why some sequences are nearly inaudible in addition to speech overlaps and background noise coming from other pupils (Figure 1b). We conclude that the multimodal differentiation takes place primarily during activity management in classroom within teacher functions, either for reminding APs of the instruction or for clarifying it. In other words, when T conveys information to all pupils (i.e. when she explains something about the didactic content), differentiation becomes almost impossible for the simple reason that she mainly addresses them as a collective body (that she prioritizes) and not as individuals. We also contend that even if she tried to resort to differentiation for a few times in favor of the APs during the general information process (on grammar, vocabulary or another linguistic point), this would probably bear the potential risk of hindering the progression of the course. In brief, we infer that T needs a kind of break between the information transmitting sequences in order to be convenient for differentiation.

Secondly, realizing that APs do not understand her instruction properly, T performs a series of kinesics to clarify it: She crouches down next to the right-hand side AP and points her index finger toward the words in the AP's notebook for meaning that the AP should consider the words written in it to complete the given task (Figure 1c). Thereafter, T brings her right hand to her mouth with a quick flick of the wrist to disambiguate the word "parler" (speak), as the task requires a summary of the author's emotions: The tips of all five fingers are gathered and curled in the palm before rubbing each other close to lips (in the form of an imaginary purse); the gesture in question is an iconic one, and it serves to illustrate the meaning of the word "speak" (Figure 1d).

3.2 Role of Proxemics in Differentiation

Concerning the use of space, the APs generally sit at the back of the classroom, which forces T to repetitive displacements between native pupils and APs when differentiation becomes necessary. In fact, the observed sequences in the corpus show the influence of spatial organization on the treatment of APs according to their position in the classroom (Azaoui & Denizci, 2022).

As it turns out, any pupil is free to choice where to sit. Nevertheless, APs may have a tendency to sit in the back rows because of shyness, probably due to their linguistic inadequacy and lack of familiarity with the culture, so that APS may be reluctant to actively participate to classroom interactions. We find this type of compartmentalized seating arrangement regarding APs ineffective and aver that it may lead to a kind of differentiator pedagogy rather than a differentiated one (Kahn, 2010). In that perspective, we may ask if it would be more efficient to advise APs to sit next to a linguistically more proficient native peer in order to enhance especially their linguistic progression (in a Vygotskian perspective) and their cultural familiarity. This way, it would be possible to not contradict the essence of differentiation, i.e. the process of accompanying the individual toward a pedagogical goal within the collectivity.

Although some of the T's kinesic behaviors stay out of camera reach because of its position, the example below illustrates this kind of isolation for an AP. T approaches him to elucidate the instruction about the activity. Interpersonal distance, gaze direction, posture, hand gestures as well as lower speech rate are all brought into play (Figure 2).

T: Michel Leiris, comment il fait pour parler *MICHEL LEIRIS, WHAT DOES HE DO TO SPEAK* <ig> (Figure 2a) de ses émotions ? *OF HIS EMOTIONS ?* <ga> (Figure 2b) Tu parles de ses émotions donc tu

YOU ARE GONNA TALK ABOUT HIS EMOTIONS SO YOU <dg> (Figure 2c) [...] le vocabulaire *THE VOCABULARY* <ga> (Figure 2d) de la trahison, de la médecine *OF BETRAYAL, OF MEDECINE* <dg> (Figure 2e). [...] Vous avez souligné *YOU HAVE UNDERLINED* <dg + ig> (Figure 2f) le vocabulaire de la trahison *THE VOCABULARY OF BETRAYAL*.

Figure 2: Multimodal Differentiation in a Fixed Proxemic Setting

While clarifying the instruction for the AP concerned, T illustrates the word “speech” with the same iconic gesture as in the previous example (Figure 2a), and she directs her gaze to AP to see his reaction (Figure 2b). Then, she points her index finger of the right hand to the words written on the whiteboard (Figure 2c) and redirects her gaze toward AP to understand once more his reaction (Figure 2d). When she says “(the vocabulary) of betrayal, of medicine”, she points her hand (deictic gesture with extended fingers and palm facing upwards) to AP, meaning that T expects an answer from AP for this activity (Figure 2e). Lastly, when she utters the word “underlined”, she performs simultaneously a deictic gesture showing the words in AP’s notebook but then, the right hand index finger sweeps the words in the notebook to illustrate the word “underlined” (Figure 2f). As far as the gestural morphology is concerned, it is an iconic gesture overlapping more or less with a deictic one.

3.3 Deictic Gestures as Practical Tools

Deictic hand gestures prove to be very practical and effective within multimodal differentiation which becomes even more evident when didactic content takes also its place in addition to process in terms of differentiation components. For example, during a collective rewriting activity concerning the modification of a text’s tense and pronouns, T provides APs with an auxiliary document in which words regarding emotions are associated to images. This auxiliary document aims to improve the writing skill of APs in relation to the collective activity. At the beginning of this sequence, T stands in front of the whiteboard. After splitting pupils into two groups (consisting of 3-4 persons for the native ones and of 2 persons for the APs), she points her index finger at APs:

T: Je vais vous donner quelque chose *I WILL GIVE YOU SOMETHING* <dg toward APs + ga>; j’arrive, une seconde *I AM COMING, JUST A SECOND*.

So, while native pupils deal with the main activity, APs start working on the auxiliary document. Next, T comes near APs and asks them:

T: Ça a été fini ? *IS THAT FINISHED?* <appr + flp> Tu as trouvé tous les mots ? *HAVE YOU MATCHED ALL WORDS?* <flp + dg toward words in the document>. As it has already been pointed out, the compartmentalized seating arrangement leads to T’s repetitive back and forth movements between APs and native pupils. Hence, after T moves away from APs to check native pupils, she comes back toward APs:

T: Vous allez faire les sentiments. D’accord ? *YOU WILL WORK ON EMOTIONS. ALL RIGHT?* <flp in front of APs>. La tristesse, la joie, la peur, la surprise, hein ? *SADNESS, JOY, FEAR, SURPRISE, OK?* <dg toward document + ga toward APs> Donc, vous regardez ça *SO, YOU LOOK AT THIS* <dg toward document>.

These sequences (like many others in the corpus) show indeed the frequent use of deictic hand gestures as practical tools. In fact, they are sometimes used to such a point that they may be qualified as monotonous. Yet, since deictic hand gestures may relate to any verbal referent according to the immediate communicative context (similarly to deictic adjectives and pronouns in verbal language such as “this”, “that”, etc.), they constitute one of the most frequent kinesic tools teachers resort to for the purpose of clarifying an explanation or conveying information.

3.4 Multimodal Coordination within Differentiation

Kinesic and proxemic behaviors of T may coordinate harmoniously. In other words, the verbal, prosodic and non-verbal strategies deployed by T prove to be conscious and fluent while passing from one modality to another. In that perspective, Azaoui (2019b) even speaks of the notion of transmodality rather than multimodality for referring to this kind of coordination witnessed in teachers’ behaviors.

Still within the framework of the example given in the previous subsection 3.3, T reinforces differentiation for the sake of clarity in terms of giving instructions to APs (Figure 3): First of all, considering the proxemics, T

moves toward APs and stands close to them with a forward leaning posture. Secondly, she depicts the word “lisez” (read) by bringing the right forefinger to her eyes and staring directly at the left-hand side AP (Figure 3a). T performs the same gesture in the same way for the right-hand side AP as well, but by leaning toward her more (Figure 3b). Meanwhile, T directs sometimes her deictic gesture to the auxiliary documents while pronouncing “read”; this way, the gesture refers to two different but related semantic contents: the act of reading and the documents on which this act will be accomplished. Lastly, T imitates in the air the act of writing with the intermediary of an iconic gesture (Figure 3c). For this whole sequence, T keeps her speech rate down, articulates her utterances clearly and accentuates words when necessary. In sum, she insists on the instruction: APs should read first and then write.

T <flp with a frontal position>: Vous lisez *YOU READ* <dg + ga> (Figure 3a). [...] Ça *THIS* <dg toward document + prosodic accentuation>, tu *YOU* <flp + ga + dg> (Figure 3b) lis *READ* <dg toward document + ga> et ça *AND THAT ONE* <dg toward other document>, c'est pour faire les exercices à la main *THAT IS FOR DOING THE WRITTEN WORKSHEET EXERCISES* <ga + ig> (Figure 3c).

Figure 3: Multimodally Coordinated Behaviors

To our point of view, the sequence above represents a good example for linking verbal, prosodic, kinesic and proxemic behaviors. They follow one another but gradually overlap to reinforce each other through diverse communicative channels.

3.5 Role of Facial Expression in Lexical Information

Another sequence of differentiation in relation to the same activity, where APs should associate some adjectives about personal characteristics to the corresponding images, shows that T's facial expressions also convey lexical information especially in solidarity with her self-touching hand gestures (Figure 4). That is to say, T's facial expressions overlapping with self-touching hand gestures serve to distinguish male and female adjectives, as French requires the agreement of adjectives with the corresponding nouns.

Overall, these two kinesic behaviors function in the same manner as iconic gestures, and they illustrate their semantic content, i.e. the adjectives “beau” (handsome) and “belle” (beautiful) respectively (Figure 4a, 4b).

Interestingly, T depicts a handsome man via a serious look, whereas a beautiful woman is described with a smile. This is probably due to the socially accepted norms attributed to men and women in terms of beauty, i.e. a handsome man would rather look serious, and a beautiful woman would instead smile.

T <flp in a frontal position>: Beau *HANDSOME* <ga + touching gesture to the cheek + fe> (Figure 4a).
Belle *BEAUTIFUL* <prosodic accentuation + ga + touching gesture under the chin + fe> (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Facial Expression Conveying Lexical Information

In consequence, facial expressions also play a role in multimodally conveying information within differentiation. Combined with self-touching gestures, they provide a visual clue to the addressee in order to deduce the semantic content of a lexical unit.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

Concerning the multimodal differentiation in the service of allophone pupils following courses together with native pupils of 3rd grade, our findings lead us to the following conclusions: First of all, in terms of prosodic elements, the teacher reduces her speech rate, articulates more her utterances and emphasizes some important words in the verbal discourse to facilitate understanding for allophone pupils. Secondly, when considering the interpersonal distances, she approaches allophone pupils generally seated at the back of the classroom (on their own choice), positions herself in front of them and adopts a forward leaning posture. Moreover, regarding the kinesic elements, she directs her gaze to allophone pupils and performs mostly deictic hand gestures to show something (e.g. a word written on the whiteboard or in the notebook, a part of her own body, an object in the classroom, etc.) but also iconic ones to illustrate a verbal referent figuring in her discourse. She sometimes resorts to facial expressions alongside with hand gestures to convey lexical information.

It should also be pointed out that the multimodal differentiation sequences mostly occur within the management of classroom activities: In such sequences, the teacher mostly focuses on allophone pupils either for clarifying her instructions or giving linguistic information in order to promote meaning within the main activity (or in the scope of an alternative activity proposed to allophone pupils for multimodally differentiating).

As it turns out, the inclusion classroom setting may present linguistic level discrepancies as well as cultural diversities. Hence, the question of how to effectively differentiate at the pedagogical level without offending allophone pupils at the cultural level arises from this setting. To our point of view, the pedagogical and cultural conclusions of multimodal differentiation may better be drawn and interpreted firstly by taking into account allophone pupils' and teachers' opinions about the matter at hand. Moreover, the efficiency of multimodal differentiation should also be assessed by considering allophone pupils' academic achievements in the long run.

At the pedagogical level, research has shown the efficiency of multimodal approaches (Azaoui, 2017b, 2019a; Castany-Owhadi & Azaoui, 2022) and the place of multimodality within differentiation (Azaoui, 2017a, 2019b; Azaoui & Denizci, 2022) in terms of teacher practices. This study also focused on multimodal differentiation rather as a process in conjunction with the above-mentioned research. Furthermore, as Benzakki and Dias Mendonça (2022) show through their survey intended for teachers (from France, Luxembourg and Québec), on

the one hand, the multimodal differentiation mostly manifests itself within teacher instructions and tasks given to pupils, and on the other hand, kinesic behaviors are cited between teacher practices contributing to differentiation. Our findings in this study are similar to theirs. Yet, the question of to what extent kinesic behaviors (and proxemic ones) serving to differentiate multimodally are conscious and systematic should be raised by further research. Irrespective of the answer, we contend that it would be opportune to integrate multimodal differentiation to the formation of pre-service and in-service teachers.

At the cultural level, it may be relevant to draw attention especially to the control of interpersonal distance by teachers and to the seating arrangement in the classroom. Our findings showed that the teacher diminished her physical distance with respect to allophone pupils in the differentiated sequences; so whether the reduced distance culturally and personally disturbs or not allophone pupils should be evidenced by further research. In addition to this, the pedagogical but mostly the psychological effects of the isolated seating arrangement (at the back of the classroom) on allophone pupils may also be investigated in future.

All in all, multimodal differentiation is very delicate in terms of delving into some pedagogical and cultural issues, as it proves to be essential for remedying pupils' problems and meeting their needs at various levels within collective pedagogical objectives. Nevertheless, its implications remain to be discovered with further research especially when considering the FFL settings in Turkey.

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